

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF IMPACT DAMAGE IN MULTI-MATERIAL AIRPLANE STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY

Bird impact damage in aircraft structure has been investigated using explicit transient dynamic analysis by ABAQUS/Explicit. Various failure modes have been investigated such as CFRP face layer rupture, damage initiation in Nomex core and elastoplastic behaviour of metallic structure. Parametric analysis has been performed using different impact locations and velocity vectors.

Keywords: sandwich, composite, airplane structure, impact damage, bird strike

INTRODUCTION

Bird strikes remain one of the major threats to the safety of air transport. It is estimated that bird strike events occur once every two thousand flights and that about 50 airplanes have been lost in civil air transport since the beginning of the human flight [1]. Most of the bird strike incidents occur during takeoff and landing phase of the flight, in which the flaps and slats are fully deflected and subjected to impacts. This paper deals with the problem of numerical prediction of damage caused by bird strikes in a typical large airliner inboard flap structure. Bird strike simulations present a interaction of complex numerical tasks including contact, various damage initiation and evolution models, failure of elements and removal of failed elements, modelling of pressures and loads exerted during the impact and others. ABAQUS/Explicit has been chosen to perform nonlinear transient numerical analyses in order to use its large library of elements and material models. The numerical procedure simulating bird strikes has been applied on a very detailed model consisting of composite laminates, sandwich structures and metallic structural items. Impacts have been applied to the flap leading edge, which is the area the most probably subjected to bird impacts due to complex and disturbed airflow around the wing. The mass of the impacting bird is chosen to be 1.81 kg (4 lbs), according to certification requirements for large transport aircraft (FAR Part 25, Subpart 25.571).

NUMERICAL MODEL

Description of the flap structure

In order to decrease the structural weight of flaps and other similar high lift and control devices, composite materials and sandwich structures are used to a large extent. The

structure of a typical large airliner flap consists of 3 spars (front, rear and auxiliary), ribs, skins and stringers. The spars and ribs are made of various aluminium alloys. The skin is made of CFRP and is additionally strengthened with 10 CFRP stringers, of which 6 are positioned along the upper skin and 4 are positioned on the lower flap skin. The leading and trailing edges of the flap are made as sandwich structures. The thin face layers of the leading edge sandwich are also made of CFRP, while Al2024 alloy was used for the flap trailing edge sandwich face layers. The number of unidirectional CFRP layers of the skin gradually varies from 14 to 41 resulting in a change of skin thickness from 1.75 to 5.125 mm. Flap geometry and layout of structural elements are shown on Figures 1 and 2.

Finite element model

The flap geometry has been mainly idealized using four and three node shell elements with reduced integration and hourglass control. Skin stringers and front spar stiffeners have been modelled using beam elements. Fig. 1 shows the finite element mesh and various types of elements employed. The mesh of internal structure has been shown on Fig. 2. The total number of finite elements is 106894, of which 63771 are shell, 16020 continuum shell, 3438 beam and 23665 solid elements.

Fig. 1. Flap geometry and finite element mesh

Special attention was given to the discretisation of leading and trailing edge sandwich structures due to their relatively large thickness. These parts of the flap have been modelled using three dimensional finite elements. The honeycomb core was modelled using standard eight node solid brick elements (C3D8), while the face layers were discretized by 8 eight node continuum shell (SC8R) elements. Continuum shell elements have kinematic and constitutive behaviour which is similar to the conventional shell elements, but enable to capture three dimensional geometry, and hence improve the accuracy in contact problems. Due to the fact that both continuum shell and solid

elements have only translational degrees of freedom, coupling at the interface of face layer and core elements is achieved by sharing the same interface nodes [2].

Fig. 2. Details of the flap structure finite element mesh

An appropriate coupling constraint needs to be provided when continuum shell elements are connected to conventional shell elements in order to correctly transfer moments, forces and rotational degrees of freedom. These kinematic coupling constraints have been applied by the tie surface based constraints, which are imposed to nodes at the linkage of the continuum shell and conventional shell elements (visible on Fig. 1).

Material constitutive models and failure modes

Material properties of aluminium alloys have been taken from [3]. In modelling the failure of metallic members, a shear failure criterion has been used and failed elements have been removed from the mesh. The shear failure criterion is suitable for high strain rate dynamic problems and is based on the accumulated equivalent plastic strain. An element is assumed to fail when the damage parameter calculated as

$$\omega = \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}_0^{pl} + \sum \Delta \bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_f^{pl}}, \quad (1)$$

exceeds the value 1 [2]. In Equation (1) $\bar{\varepsilon}_f^{pl}$ is the strain at failure, $\bar{\varepsilon}_0^{pl}$ is the initial value of equivalent plastic strain, $\Delta \bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}$ is the plastic strain increment, and the summation is performed over all increments in the analysis. Mechanical properties of unidirectional CFRP layers have been taken from [4]. A progressive failure and damage model was used to model failure in the CFRP section of the structure. The ABAQUS built-in progressive damage and failure model for fibre reinforced polymers uses Hashin's failure initiation criterion and accounts for the following failure modes: fibre

rupture in tension, fibre buckling and kinking in compression, matrix cracking under transverse tension and shearing, matrix crushing under transverse compression and shearing. Degradation of CFRP material stiffness is modelled using damage parameters, which modify the initially undamaged elasticity matrix. Fibre (d_f), matrix (d_m) and shear (d_s) damage parameters reflect the current state of damage, having values ranging from 0 for an undamaged state, to 1 for a completely degraded material. The damaged elasticity matrix has the form

$$\mathbf{C}_d = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)E_1 & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)\nu_{21}E_1 & 0 \\ (1-d_f)(1-d_m)\nu_{12}E_2 & (1-d_m)E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-d_s)G_{12}D \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $D = 1 - (1-d_f)(1-d_m)\nu_{12}\nu_{21}$, while $E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \nu_{12}$, and ν_{21} are the material properties. Damage variables will evolve in a such way so that the stress-displacement relation is depicted in Fig. 3, left-hand image. In order to avoid mesh dependency during material softening, ABAQUS uses a constitutive law expressed as a stress - equivalent displacement relation. The positive slope (line OA) of the stress-displacement curve corresponds to the linear elastic material behaviour prior to the damage initiation, while the negative slope (line AC) is achieved by degradation of material stiffness after the damage onset. Unloading and reloading from a partially damaged state occurs along a linear path toward the origin represented by the line BO (or OB for reloading) path on Fig. 4, left-hand image. The area of the triangle OAC equals energy dissipated due to the damage. After damage initiation, damage parameters of particular failure modes evolve as shown on Fig. 3, right-hand image. An element is removed from the mesh when all material points reach the critical degradation value.

Fig. 3. Equivalent stress-displacement diagram (left-hand image) and damage variable as a function of equivalent displacement (right-hand image) [2]

Mechanical properties of Nomex honeycomb core are taken from [5]. Sandwich structures show characteristic behaviour when compressive loads are applied. The generic compressive stress-strain curve of Nomex honeycomb core (Fig. 5) can be divided into three distinctive regions. The first region corresponds to a linearly elastic region which is present at low strains (typically 0.5-5%). The next step is progressive core crushing at a nearly constant stress level called the plateau stress. At a strain value

of about 85%, a stiffening occurs caused by the mutual pressing of cell walls. To simulate core crushing and puncture under impact loads, the above explained shear failure criterion was adopted to remove core finite elements from the mesh when an equivalent plastic strain of 5% has been reached. The plateau stress (σ_{pl}) value is taken to be 7.76 MPa [5].

Fig. 4. Compressive stress-strain curve of Nomex honeycomb core (after [5])

As ABAQUS doesn't offer the ability to model composite beam elements, the problem of modelling composite stringers has been solved by calculating homogenized material properties following a method derived in [6]. This procedure replaces the composite beam with a beam of equivalent isotropic material properties. For a simple rectangular shaped stringer the procedure consists of calculating the equivalent beam stiffness as

$$ES = \int_S E_i dS = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i S_i, \quad EI_z = \int_S E_i y^2 dS = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i I_{zi}, \quad GS = \int_S G_i dS = \sum_{i=1}^n G_i S_i, \quad (3)$$

where n denotes the number of layers applied in the design of stringer. The values of areas S_i and moments of inertia I_{zi} are calculated for every unidirectional composite layer. Material properties E_i and G_i refer to the beam global coordinate system (x,y,z). For layers oriented at an angle θ with respect to the beam coordinate system, mechanical properties have to be transformed from the material coordinate system ($1,2,3$) using well known expressions, eg. [4]. Final expressions required to calculate replacement material properties are

$$E_{eq} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n E_i S_i}{S}, \quad I_{zeq} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n E_i I_{zi}}{E_{eq}}, \quad G_{eq} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n G_i S_i}{S}. \quad (4)$$

In this research, impact has been applied to the leading edge only, where no stringers are present, and therefore there was no need to introduce a failure criterion for beam elements.

Bird model verification

The validity of numerical bird strike simulations critically depends on the correct modelling of forces and pressures imposed to the impacted structure. Bird strikes always occur at relatively high speeds, resulting in local stresses in bird which are

higher than the homogenized material strength, leading to a “flow” of bird material, thus spreading the impact forces over a wider area. This means that the bird material strength can be neglected, placing bird strikes in the group of soft body impacts. Usual practice in finite element simulations of bird strikes is to replace the bird with an equivalent mass of water [1, 8, 10]. Hydrodynamic response of bird substitute material is modelled with the equation of state (EOS) materials, which define the material's volumetric strength and pressure to density ratio.

Important results and conclusions for bird strike analyses are available in [7]. It has been concluded that the most suitable substitute material was gelatine with 10% porosity and a density of about 950 kg/m^3 . Another important conclusion was that the most suitable shape of the impacting body is a cylinder with hemispherical ends and a length to diameter ratio equal to 2. In reference [8] it has been suggested that the Hugoniot pressure for an impact at 116 m/s should be near the theoretical value of 93.6 MPa . After extensive literature survey and rigid target bird validation impact analyses, it has been decided to use EOS properties defined in [9]. The bird material density was assumed to be 938 kg/m^3 , as to take into account 10% bird material porosity due to trapped air in the lungs and bones. A Lagrangian bird model was used consisting of 1388 hexahedral solid finite elements with viscous hourglass control and distortion controls to counter the excessive element distortion. The bird finite element model is shown on Fig. 5. Validation of the bird model has been done by comparing Hugoniot and stagnation pressures developed in an impact on a rigid target at a velocity of 116 m/s , normal to the plate. The results are shown on Fig. 5. The pressure values match well the theoretical values, providing confidence in the applied bird model.

Fig. 5. Bird validation results: Pressure distribution (left-hand image), deformed bird model after 0.001 s (upper right-hand image), bird finite element mesh (lower right-hand image, dimensions in mm)

ANALYSIS

Two impact cases have been analysed in this work. Impacts have been applied on the flap leading edge which is usually exposed to bird strike due to the complicated airflow around the flap. Bird initial velocity is 100 m/s at two different flap deflection angles (20° and 40°) added to the assumed aircraft angle of attack of 20° during landing or

takeoff resulting in velocity vectors deflected 40° and 60° with respect to the flap referent horizontal plane. Fig. 6 shows the impact location on the flap and gives explanation of bird initial velocity vectors. The velocity vector has components only in the (y,z) plane (Fig. 6) as the inboard flap is orthogonal to the airplane's plane of symmetry. A time interval of 0.006 s is enough to simulate the entire impact event. General contact algorithm was used to impose the forces and pressures exerted during the impact on the flap. The general contact option uses the penalty contact algorithm and is the default method to simulate contact problems in ABAQUS/Explicit. General contact is particularly suited to handle complex contact conditions between different bodies and within the same body (self contact) making it appropriate for bird strike simulations in which element failure criteria are employed.

RESULTS

Results are presented for two analysed impact cases: 40° deflection of velocity vector (case 1) and 60° deflection of velocity vector (case 2). Both analysed scenarios demonstrate that the kinetic energy of the bird is sufficient to easily penetrate the leading edge sandwich structure causing heavy damage to the front spar and ribs. The results show that the created damage is localised to the impact area and that the rest of the structure is relatively unaffected by the impacting loads. This means that for bird strike induced damage prediction, an analysis on a part of the flap structure is sufficient, thereby reducing computational cost and output file size. The time histories of Von Mises stress and penetration of flap structure for case 1 are shown on Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. Impact locations and bird initial velocity vectors

Fig. 8 (left) shows contour plot of equivalent plastic strain in the front spar and rib for the first impact case at the end of the simulation. None of the rib and spar elements have failed but values of equivalent plastic strain show that in some of the rib elements strains are close to 15%, which is the failure strain for Al 2024 alloys. Displacement - time diagram of the front spar location at which the bird initially impacts is shown on Fig. 8, right-hand image. The sudden increase of displacements shows that the bird impacts on the front spar at 0.003 s after the start of analysis. The maximal displacement is 0.022 m.

Fig. 7. Time history of Von Mises stress - Case 1 (cross sectional view)

Fig. 9 shows energy history for the first impact case. At 0.003 s, a sudden drop in kinetic energy (ALLKE) occurs, due to the fact that the bird impacts on the front spar and loses its speed rapidly. The lost kinetic energy is converted into internal (ALLIE), plastic (ALLPD) and elastic deformation (ALLSE) energies that increase significantly. It is evident that the artificial strain energy (ALLAE) has large values due to the large hourglass control forces used to avoid excessive deformation of bird elements, thus eliminating numerical problems. Both impact cases result with similar energy history diagrams.

Fig 8. Equivalent plastic strain in front spar and rib - Case 1 (left-hand image); y direction displacement history of initial impact front spar location - Case 1 (right-hand image)

Fig. 9. Energy history for the whole model - case 1

Fig. 11 shows the failure of the flap leading edge sandwich structure at the second impact case. Elements of the honeycomb core reach the specified failure criterion very early in the deformation process and are removed from the mesh, simulating the core crushing behaviour, as explained earlier. Fibre rupture in tension is the critical failure mode of most CFRP face layer elements. As illustrated on Fig. 9, only about 25% of bird kinetic energy was absorbed during core crushing and sandwich structural failure.

Fig. 11. Crushing of honeycomb core - case 2

CONCLUSIONS

This paper shows the numerical prediction of bird strike induced damage on the structure of a typical large airliner inboard flap. The results show that a 4 lb bird impact, which is used for certification requirements, causes severe damage to the flap structure. Impact velocity vectors were varied always resulting in the penetration of the leading edge sandwich structure and damage to the front spar and ribs. Despite many possible

sources for appearance of numerical instabilities the analyses remained stable and robust. A number of material models has been considered to correctly simulate bird behaviour, resulting in appropriate EOS material and the typical shape for numerical bird strike analyses. The results of bird model validation show good correlation with theory and other published references.

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